

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING HISTORY

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Abstract. *The science of history as an independent social science with its place at all stages of education is considered important in the upbringing of a harmonious generation. This article discusses how to more effectively organize historical education by analyzing national and foreign literature.*

Keywords: *effective teaching, history teaching, effective history teaching, historical empathy.*

During the years of independence, the objective study of the history of Uzbekistan, the correct assessment of the ancient and rich history of the Uzbek people became a priority. In the shadow of independence, which took a sharp turn in the life and fate of the Uzbek people, Science, in particular history, which was the basis of national identity and spiritual ascension, also developed in its own way. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev's work "we will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan together", "... we believe that in-depth study of advanced world experiences is one of the important conditions for the implementation of a wide range of tasks ahead of us to be implemented in Practice" [1, 27].

"Education" in a broad sense is a general process directed towards the continuous transmission of experiences of great social importance, established by previous generations, and in a narrow sense, a social institution, one of the social substructures of society. And "quality" as a philosophical term is the sum of all the important properties of an object or object. Harmonizing the essence of the concepts of "education" and "quality", the quality of education, this is a process consisting in the combination of the most convenient methods that serve for the integrity of its characteristics, the education of the learner and his personal development [7,5].

The quality of education is a process in which the qualitative tasks of the components of the entire educational system have a complex development Force (Dynamics), which is explained by changes in the activities of educational institutions, that is, by changes in their social, economic, technological and political environment [8,181]. At the same time, the quality of modern education is not one of the results of innovative development, but one of the prerequisites for its implementation [9, 4].

The concept of history, this field of study, as a scientific field and science, is the process of studying the actions and activities made by people over time. However, it is impossible to learn and reveal everything that happened in the historical process. Because, as stated in the positive view of history, any claim that can be taken as a historical reference must be based on evidence, especially written evidence. Therefore, history can be described as written information about the events and arguments of the past. J. Slater expresses this view as follows: ".....in essence, history is a way of exploring the past and simultaneously validating our knowledge and thoughts" [10, 8].

The western counterpart of the concept of history, "history", belongs to ancient Greek and Means "exploration" or research of reality. As a discipline, history studies human history through its unique methodology.

Historical methodology consists in identifying the field of research, problem or topic, developing hypotheses related to this topic or problem, collecting information from the evidence and sources obtained, analyzing and criticizing this information, considering other research on the topic and understanding the topic, as well as revealing the research explained on a logical basis, based on this, studying the past in the process, the creation of real and complete concepts or images and thinking about all these stages is defined as such.

When organizing traditional history classes, the process of transferring information to students is usually carried out by reading a textbook or other secondary ready-made sources. This process generates a skill for the learner to remember and perceive ready-made information as information. Unconventional interdisciplinary, while effective history classes emphasize the use of the aforementioned skills and history teaching methodology to achieve credible definitions and explanations of the past. Because the pedagogical and historical research methods used in history lessons and history research can give students a variety of useful facilities in understanding the past. The process of studying sources and identifying written evidence, identifying the personal opinions of the person(s) who prepared the source or the evidence given, and studying the true meaning of the opinions presented in written or other sources, is another aspect of history teaching. This means teaching how historical reality can be studied. Effective history teaching requires students to provide resources and Dalis along with ready-made historically inferred data. The fact that the reader, analyzing certain historical sources (whether written or oral), generates historical knowledge and imagination is extremely effective from a pedagogical point of view. Already, in history lessons, it is considered useful to use methods that ensure the independent thinking of the educator, rather than those that stimulate the memory of him. To understand historical knowledge and understand the past, it is necessary to study and examine the evidence. But the elements that make up history are not only about them, but also the events of the past, a complex of isolates known today. Some researchers argue that the practice of teaching history using historical thought processes makes an important contribution to the understanding of many historical problems and topics. Today, the modern state of education is the concept of Education, which requires direct consideration and clarification, access to the process of analyzing the categories and principles of personality-oriented pedagogy. The new model of pedagogical consciousness gradually renounces the teacher's practice of direct influence on the learner and allows for a more efficient organization of the structure of the entire pedagogical space to ensure the learner's own development opportunities. Thus, each teacher strives to make their lessons interesting and meaningful, which increases the interest of the learners in the subject. In particular, in history lessons, special attention is paid not to the assimilation of facts, but to the development of personality through the development of the values of different eras, the ability to put oneself in the place of a person of the past, to understand his thoughts, actions. All this can be done with the help of historical empathy.

The use of samples of fiction in history lessons also helps to clarify historical reality, create vivid images of the past. In addition, the use of different manifestations in the narration of historical events is samrali. For example, these include pictorial manifestations of objects of material culture, technical(audio-visual) means of training. All this allows readers to imagine the atmosphere of a historical period, to experience a feeling of feeling within historical phenomena in the past.

Another way in which historical empathy is formed is through personality. The idea of Destinies, actions, life circumstances in the soul of the educator, the functioning of a historical person makes it possible to understand the state and activity of a Taihi person as a typical phenomenon in social life [12, 240].

The formation of historical empathy includes the following tasks:

- Imaginary journey. In the course of a history lesson, it is required to describe what we can see the person of the past. For example: "I go to the Kokand Khanate of the XVIII century and...", "...let's get into the feudal Castle..." with the help of an introduction to the historical period in which the learners are studied, the organization of historical travel is considered one of the ways of forming historical empathy. The positive aspect of such tasks is that educators pay attention to historical details .

- Fictional interview. One student becomes a historical figure, and the rest of the students ask him questions. Questions asked are required to relate to the life and work of the historical hero. This type of assignment requires good training of lesson participants who are able to complete the previous task.

- Unfinished sentence method-a historical person is asked to continue a phrase that belongs, for example, to the Sahibqiran Amir Temur. ("We Stand who is civil..."). Thus it is proposed to carry out the experience of predicting the end of any historical vogeas.

- Historical choice - "... how would you do", "...who would you like ?", "Which category are you for?" , and b.». On the basis of these questions, the educator will be able to make decisions and determine the side in the place of historical figures, feeling historical phenomena in himself. Foreign Methodists suggest using the following tasks in the course of the lesson: "if you are 15-year-old King Richard III, What do you feel when fighting rebels in peasant uprisings? Would you agree to their demands?"

When performing this task, students will have to not only know historical materials, but also present their point of view on the problem through the analysis of existing knowledge.

- Reconstructed painting-acquaintance with monologues or conversations of historical paintings. When performing this type of assignment, students are required to clearly imagine that they must demonstrate historical knowledge, so this task can be carried out not only on the basis of a textbook, but also with the involvement of additional literature.

First-person composition - based on scrolls, memoirs, diary entries using various genres - tells about the events of the past on behalf of a witness or participant.

In the process of teaching history and historical research, educational participants and researchers are faced with an important task related to language, such as understanding, interpreting and using historical terms and concepts. According to the English researcher Graham Swift in *Husbands*, to have concepts about the past in different ways, historical persones which are used by historians to interpret their views, beliefs and activities and to represent historical processes, a special language that combines historical expressions and concepts is called "historical language" [13,16] .

The unique mission of a history teacher is to provide it with maturity to the future while teaching historical concepts. To ensure the effectiveness of teaching history, a history teacher is required to have a certain level of knowledge and some teaching skills, and to possess transformation, interpretation, evaluation, analysis, and synthesis skills and skills to understand and explain historical events, facts, people, processes, and identity. The preparation of materials,

such as geography, civic knowledge, due to their relationship with other social sciences in the process of teaching history, the use of information in the disciplines of religious culture and ethics students, not only helps to better study topics, but also gives the opportunity to perceive social realities in general and understand real life.

In the course of the lesson, it is very important and useful to use historical materials and resources (historical documents, historical objects, pictures, maps). In addition, the use of ICT and the internet in history lessons not only contributes to the mental development of students, but also increases their level of historical thinking and learning.

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